

Analysis of genetic and genotype × environment interaction effects on heterosis of nutrient quality traits in indica hybrid rice

Chunhai Shi and Jun Zhu, Agronomy Department Zhejiang Agricultural University (ZAU); Yonggui Yu, Xiaoe Yang, and Jianming Xue, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, ZAU, Hangzhou 310029, China

Nine cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines and five restorer lines of indica rice were used in an incomplete diallel cross (9 × 5) for 2 yr. The CMS lines were Zhexie 2 A, Xieqingzao A, Zhenan 3 A, Gangchao 1 A, Yinchai 1 A, Erjiuqing A, V20A, Zuo 5 A, and Zhenshan 97 A and the five restoring lines were T49, Cezao 2-2, 26715, 102, and 1391. They were randomly sampled from a reference population. Seedlings of parents and F₁s with three replications were planted in the field experimental farm at ZAU. Seeds were sown on 28 Mar 1994 and 3 Apr 1995, and single plants of 31-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing, 24 plants in each plot. Seed samples of parents and F₁ and F₂ plants were derived at maturity from eight plants in the middle part of the plot. The F₁ seeds which were harvested from female parents were obtained by crossing CMS lines to restorer lines at flowering. Quantitative traits of rice nutrient quality (see table) were measured with three replications for each sample of parents, F₁s, and F₂s.

The components of heterosis of seed traits for F₂ over the mean of parents

$$H = [F_2 - \frac{P_1 + P_2}{2}] / \mu$$

were predicted for various types of heterosis (see table). We found that nutrient quality of milled rice from these hybrids was influenced by seed, cytoplasmic, and maternal heterosis (see table). Interaction was larger than genetic heterosis, and was associated with increased nutrient quality traits in 1994 but not in 1995; similarly total heterosis was larger in 1994 than in 1995. Maternal heterosis (-0.04) and

Mean (range) of heterosis for nutrient quality traits of F₂ seed in indica hybrid rice. Hangzhou, China, 1994-95.

Parameter	Genetic heterosis	Interaction heterosis in 1994	Interaction heterosis in 1995
<i>Protein content</i>			
Direct heterosis	0.02 (-0.02 ~ 0.05)	0.17 (-0.03 ~ 0.36)	-0.06 (-0.21 ~ 0.13)
Cytoplasmic heterosis	-0.03 (-0.09 ~ 0.04)	0.04 (-0.07 ~ 0.15)	-0.08 (-0.16 ~ 0.04)
Maternal heterosis	-0.04 (-0.21 ~ 0.11)	-0.01 (-0.27 ~ 0.21)	-0.08 (-0.36 ~ 0.14)
<i>Protein index</i>			
Direct heterosis	0.01 (-0.02 ~ 0.04)	0.13 (-0.00 ~ 0.38)	-0.05 (-0.22 ~ 0.15)
Cytoplasmic heterosis	0.02 (-0.07 ~ 0.13)	0.10 (-0.06 ~ 0.27)	-0.07 (-0.19 ~ -0.01)
Maternal heterosis	0.00 (-0.09 ~ 0.15)	0.06 (-0.25 ~ 0.39)	-0.06 (-0.35 ~ 0.13)
<i>Lysine content</i>			
Direct heterosis	0.02 (-0.07 ~ 0.15)	0.16 (-0.12 ~ 0.75)	-0.08 (-0.50 ~ 0.28)
Cytoplasmic heterosis	na	0.13 (-0.11 ~ 0.39)	-0.16 (-0.39 ~ 0.04)
Maternal heterosis	-0.01 (-0.12 ~ 0.09)	0.11 (-0.45 ~ 0.83)	-0.17 (-0.76 ~ 0.60)
<i>Lysine index</i>			
Direct heterosis	0.02 (-0.14 ~ 0.19)	0.11 (-0.15 ~ 0.66)	-0.06 (-0.46 ~ 0.33)
Cytoplasmic heterosis	na	0.19 (-0.08 ~ 0.58)	-0.14 (-0.38 ~ 0.14)
Maternal heterosis	0.01 (-0.22 ~ 0.21)	0.18 (-0.41 ~ 0.96)	-0.13 (-0.79 ~ 0.60)

cytoplasmic heterosis (0.02) were the main components in genetic heterosis for protein content (PC) and protein index (PI), respectively. For interaction heterosis in 1994, direct interaction heterosis were larger for PC, PI, and lysine content (LC) traits, but cytoplasmic interaction heterosis was larger for the lysine index (LI) trait. Otherwise, interaction heterosis in 1995 mainly came from cytoplasmic

heterosis for PI and LI, maternal and cytoplasmic interaction heterosis for PC, and maternal interaction heterosis for LC. Crosses such as V20 A/26715, which had significant genetic and interaction heterosis in 1994, could increase PC and PI. Crosses such as Yinchao 1 A/T49 and Zhexie 2 A/26715, which had significant genetic interaction heterosis in 1994, could increase LC and LI, respectively. ■

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- be original work,
- have international or pan-national relevance,
- be conducted during the immediate past three years or be work in progress,
- have rice environment relevance,
- advance rice knowledge,
- use appropriate research design and data collection methodology,
- report pertinent, adequate data,
- apply appropriate statistical analysis, and
- reach supportable conclusions.

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.